

Data Center Infrastructure in the Context of National Resilience. Existing Risks, Solutions, and Prospects

The use of data centers is becoming increasingly popular due to the constant growth of data, as well as the convenience and accessibility of cloud services for users. Indeed, data centers offer a number of advantages over client-hosted local solutions, as the data center assumes the risks associated with the security of this data and the continuous availability of digital services for the data center's clients. At the same time, the irreversible process of migration to data centers makes them de facto critical infrastructure objects. These facilities must meet heightened requirements for security and operational reliability, as they have a significant impact on national resilience.

The basis for such requirements lies in the risk analysis for data centers. A data center risk is understood as the impact of uncertainty on the goals of the data center. In this context, uncertainty is explained as the lack of sufficient information to prevent a negative event. Thus, the question arises of identifying and classifying the risks associated with data centers. Naturally, data centers, as an organizational and technical system consisting of organizational processes, technical means, and tools, inherit a range of risks typical of standard information and communication systems (hereafter referred to as ICS), such as cyberattacks, physical destruction, and so on. However, due to their unique characteristics, data centers also face a number of specific risks, which are the focus of this publication.

Thus, the purpose of this study is to analyze these unique risks, propose solutions to enhance the resilience of data centers, and explore prospects for their further development.

To identify the specific risks of data centers, it is appropriate to compare them with conventional information and communication systems (ICS). First and foremost, data centers differ in terms of data volumes, the amount of equipment, monitoring challenges [1], energy supply requirements, compatibility issues of virtual machines within a single network [2-4], risks of battery failures [5,6] and equipment breakdowns, as well as failures in ventilation and fire suppression systems. Moreover, data centers face physical risks, such as floods, fires, and terrorist attacks [7]. Unlike conventional systems, relocating a data center to mitigate risks requires significant time and logistical resources, making this process comparable to a full restoration of IT infrastructure.

This study examines existing literature and models related to these issues, including traffic encryption during migration, intelligent monitoring systems, and predictive maintenance of equipment. Alternative approaches, such as hybrid

migration strategies—partly physical and partly through data transmission networks—are also analyzed. Particular attention is given to emerging practices, such as mobile data centers and geographically distributed backup strategies.

Thus, the first risk specific to data centers is the lack of adequate conditions for deployment at a new location. The next risk is the insufficiency of logistical resources for relocation. A lack of time for the migration process is also a significant risk. Furthermore, a shortage of competencies necessary for redeploying the data center at the new location may cause substantial delays in restoring operations.

An alternative approach may involve accepting the risk of losing IT equipment while ensuring data preservation. At the same time, the issue arises of the time required to create a complete backup and the availability of storage capacity in a geographically remote backup facility. It should also be noted that migrating a virtual machine is critical for load balancing, server consolidation, and maintenance in virtualized data centers, and can increase security risks. As an alternative, migration traffic should be encrypted, eliminating the need for dedicated management networks while ensuring data security and mutual authentication. The work [8] proposes an architecture that helps create an automated intelligent system, which monitors overloads or underloads and determines when operational migration should occur. Once a virtual machine is selected, encryption is performed using the appropriate security algorithm, ensuring data security, mutual authentication, confidentiality, and integrity.

It is also important to note that a critical factor here is the monitoring of the lifespan of hard drives. Thus, premature failure of a disk and the corresponding data loss can have catastrophic consequences. To reduce the risk of failures, cloud storage providers monitor the health of disks based on their status and replace hard drives before they fail. By assessing the remaining lifespan of hard drives, it is possible to predict the mean time to failure of a specific device and replace it at the appropriate time, ensuring maximum utilization while minimizing operational costs. The work [9] presents an LSTM encoder-decoder model, where the context derived from understanding the sequences of reliability statistics helps predict the output sequence of the number of days remaining until a potential disk failure. The models developed in this work have been trained and validated on a comprehensive dataset of all 10 years of S.M.A.R.T. health data provided by Backblaze, across various disk instances. A hybrid approach, where part of the data is physically moved with the media (disks), and part is transferred via data transmission networks, may also be used as an alternative. However, it is essential to consider the reliability of the data transmission channels, which presents an additional risk.

During military conflicts, the assessment of such risks increases significantly, leading to the emergence of alternative approaches to the placement of data centers

in areas that are difficult for the enemy to access. For example, Fortnox in the Swiss mountains [10], Microsoft's underwater data centers [11], and so on. Currently, there are mobile data centers, consisting of several machines (operator and administrator units) [12], as well as space-based data centers [13].

The complexity of finding an optimal solution to overcome the resilience problem of data centers can be seen as a multi-criteria task for determining optimal decisions regarding the architecture and placement of data centers. For example, the work [14] proposes a strategy for placing a backup data processing center, considering emergencies and evacuation, with a global view of network resources in scenarios defined by software. Specifically, to reduce the risk of backup loss and enable rapid evacuation after a natural disaster, the researchers examine expected losses after the disaster and evacuation delays, formulating a new facility location problem accounting for disaster and evacuation (NP-hard), which is multi-objective. The proposed multi-objective optimization algorithm optimizes multiple goals, with different coefficients in various disaster situations. In particular, data on location, backup evacuation delay, Pareto recommendation degree, and node damage loss are introduced to guide the solution search.

The work [15] investigates the impact of various uncertainties in parameters on energy efficiency and over-provisioning coefficients, such as virtual machine resource requirements, migration-related costs, or the energy consumption model of the servers used. It is demonstrated that allocating additional resources to handle workload uncertainty affects the server over-provisioning ratio and energy consumption. The paper proposes an approach for operators to calculate a more reliable migration schedule, which will lead to higher overall energy consumption. A riskier operator may choose a more favorable schedule, resulting in lower energy consumption but also increasing the risk of SLA violations.

A special case is data evacuation to avoid the consequences of cyberattacks on virtual machines by moving them to quarantine and inspection centers. The work [16] demonstrates an approach to minimizing the damage caused by a cyberattack through the rapid relocation of virtual machines under threat of malware infection to other locations, taking into account alerts provided by intrusion detection mechanisms. Specifically, the problem is formalized into a mathematical model, which is represented as an integer linear programming problem.

An additional risk during migration is the overload of physical machines. The work [17] presents a migration strategy considering workload, called Chameleon, which is focused on recent cloud workloads. Chameleon creates a new indicator and corresponding threshold value for accurately identifying hotspots. It also predicts the resource requirements of a virtual machine under complex workloads to avoid

secondary overload of the physical machine to which the virtual machine is migrated.

The main principle of migration remains the geographical distribution of data. For better availability and fault tolerance of data copies in geographically distributed data centers, the process of geo-replication is used. A distinctive feature of geo-replication is the high global latency between data centers, which varies significantly depending on the location of the data centers. Thus, the choice of data centers for deploying a cloud application directly affects the observed response time. The study [18] proposes an optimization system that automatically generates a geo-replication placement plan to minimize latency.

After the migration (copying) is completed, there remains the risk of improper data storage. The work [19] proposes an external auditor, who, on behalf of the users, will periodically check the integrity of the data stored on the cloud server. The user will not experience any online load, and data security will be maintained, as data will not be directly transmitted to the external auditor. A homomorphic encryption scheme is used to encrypt the data that will be transmitted to the Third-Party Auditor.

For continuous monitoring of data security, the authors of the work [20] propose a risk assessment framework to study the security risks of cloud operators between cloud users and two cloud providers. The risk assessment framework uses the National Vulnerability Database [21] to study the vulnerabilities of router operating systems in the cloud operator. This framework provides quantitatively defined security indicators for each cloud operator, enabling cloud users to choose the quality of security services among cloud providers.

Based on the analysis presented above, it becomes possible to classify the risks of data centers (see Table 1).

Table 1 – Classification of Data Center Risks

Risk Category	Examples	Description
Cyber Threats	Malware, ransomware, unauthorized access	Vulnerabilities in security systems that can be exploited by hackers.
Physical Risks	Natural disasters, terrorist attacks	Damage to infrastructure caused by external factors.
Equipment Risks	Hard drive failures, ventilation issues	Premature hardware failures requiring monitoring.
Logistical Risks	Insufficient resources for relocation, virtual	Challenges in transferring or deploying

	machine compatibility issues	data centers in new environments.
Energy Risks	Power interruptions	Lack of backup power sources or insufficient capacity.
Data Migration Risks	Compatibility issues, security vulnerabilities	Difficulties in transferring data between data centers or securing them.

Although the solutions presented above offer significant improvements, their implementation poses certain challenges. For instance, predictive maintenance models require extensive datasets, which are not always available. Encrypted migration enhances security but can increase latency and resource requirements. Geo-replication, while highly reliable, causes delays due to network latency and depends on a stable connection between data centers.

In times of war or similar crises, risk assessment becomes more critical, requiring unconventional data center placement strategies, such as remote mountain sites or underwater installations. However, these innovative approaches require significant investment and further technological development.

This research identifies key risks associated with data centers, distinguishing them from traditional ICS. Unique risks, such as relocation challenges, equipment failures, and vulnerabilities in virtual machine migration, were analyzed along with corresponding solutions. Techniques such as predictive maintenance, encrypted migration, and geo-replication have proven effective in improving resilience.

The findings emphasize the importance of developing innovative approaches, including mobile and autonomous data centers, to address evolving challenges. Future research should focus on optimizing algorithms for disaster recovery and exploring new technologies to ensure the resilience and sustainability of data centers under extreme conditions.

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